

Studies on Some N-Acyl-N-Phenyl Hydroxylamines as Metal Complexing Ligands : Part II. Acetyl and Monochloroacetyl Derivatives

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In a previous communication¹ the preparation of *N*-, *m* and *p* nitrobenzoyl *N*-phenylhydroxylamines and some metal chelates with those ligands are reported. Now studies on *N*-acetyl-*N*-phenylhydroxylamine and *N*-monochloroacetyl-*N*-phenylhydroxylamine have been made. *N*-acetyl-*N*-phenylhydroxylamine was first prepared by Bamberger and Destraz^{2,3}. Gupta and Sogani prepared it by a modification of the original method⁴ and reported the formation of three different complexes with Fe(III) in solution by spectrophotometric study. An aluminium complex of the same ligand was isolated by Neunhoeffler and Ruske⁵. The present authors have prepared the Cu(II), Ni(II), Fe(III), Al(III), V(V) and U(VI) chelates of both ligands and their properties have been studied.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of N-acetyl-N-phenylhydroxylamine : This compound could be best prepared by acidifying the copper chelate with dilute sulphuric acid. On evaporating the dried ethereal extract in a vacuum desiccator over sulphuric acid, crystals were separated. Found : m.p. 66.5°.

Preparation of N-monochloroacetyl-N-phenylhydroxylamine : This compound was prepared by a modification of the procedure adopted for the nitrobenzoyl-*N*-phenylhydroxylamines¹. It was recrystallised from aqueous ethanol. White, shining, needle-shaped crystals were obtained. (m.p. 128°C. Found : N, 7.51%; Cl, 19.19%; C₈H₈O₂NCl requires N, 7.55; Cl 19.14%).

Unlike the *N*-acetyl derivative this compound is sparingly soluble in water and slightly soluble in benzene. The compound is soluble in ethanol, methanol, acetone, ether but practically insoluble in petroleum ether.

1. N. N. Ghosh and G. Siddhanta, *This Journal*, 1968, **45**, 1049.
2. E. Bamberger and H. Destraz, *Ber.*, 1902, **35**, 1883.
3. E. Bamberger, *Ber.*, 1918, **51**, 636.
4. H. K. L. Gupta and N. C. Sogani, *This Journal*, 1960, **37**, 769; 1964, **41**, 91.
5. O. Neunhoeffler and E. Ruske, *Chem. Ber.*, 1961, **94**, 623.

These two ligands contain one replaceable hydrogen. They are represented by

Preparation of metal chelates :

A. *With N-acetyl-N-phenylhydroxylamine.*

Copper (II) chelate : To an aqueous solution of copper acetate (1.1 moles) an aqueous solution of the reagent (2 moles) was added. pH of the solution was raised with aqueous ammonia. The compound separated was washed successively with water and ether and finally air dried.

Nickel (II) chelate : Same as Cu(II) chelate.

Iron (III) chelate : To an aqueous solution of ferric chloride (1 mole) an aqueous solution of the reagent (3.5 moles) was added. A red colour developed. An aqueous solution of sodium acetate was added with stirring to raise the pH—when a red compound separated. Shining crystals obtained were washed with water and ether and finally air dried.

At 110–115° it lost in weight and the loss corresponded to 1.5 molecules of water. (Loss found 4.91%; calculated for 1.5H₂O, 5.06%).

Aluminium (III) chelate : Same as Fe(III) chelate. It contains no water molecules.

Vanadium (V) chelate : To an aqueous solution of sodium vanadate (1.1 moles) an aqueous solution of the reagent (2 moles) was added. The resulting yellow solution was diluted to 100 ml and dil. HCl was added until the pH was 1–1.5. The compound separated was washed with water and air dried.

Uranium (VI) chelate : To an aqueous solution of uranyl acetate (1 mole) aqueous solution of the reagent (2.2 moles) was added with stirring. The resulting orange solution was diluted to 50 ml and sodium acetate solution was added with stirring until precipitation occurred. Stirring was continued for 15 mins. The compound separated was washed with water and air dried.

B. *With N-monochloroacetyl-N-phenylhydroxylamine*

This reagent is sparingly soluble in water. Therefore ethanolic solution of the reagent was used for preparation of metal chelates and compounds separated have been washed with aqueous ethanol. Methods of preparation of various metal chelates were identical with those of the corresponding N-acetyl-N-phenylhydroxylamine chelates,

The compounds were then analysed. Magnetic properties of some of them have been studied. They appear to be high spin complexes. Results of analyses are recorded in the table below.

TABLE

Compound	Colour	pH of pptn.	Metal		Nitrogen		μ_B B.M.
			Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	
$\text{Cu}[\text{R}_{Ac}]_2$	Green	3.0—3.5	17.28	17.48	7.82	7.70	1.79
$\text{Ni}[\text{R}_{Ac}]_2$	Light green	4.0—4.5	16.18	16.36	7.73	7.80	3.11
$\text{Fe}[\text{R}_{Ac}]_3, 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Bright red	1.0—1.5	10.61	10.48	7.78	7.88	5.94
$\text{Al}[\text{R}_{Ac}]_3$	White	3.0—3.5	5.65	5.66	8.63	8.80	—
$\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{R}_{Ac})_2$	Deep violet	1.0—1.5	13.55	13.26	7.20	7.29	Dia
$\text{UO}_2(\text{R}_{Ac})_2$	Orange yellow	4.5—5.0	41.16	41.76	4.85	4.91	—
$\text{Cu}[\text{R}_{ClAc}]_2$	Green	3.5—4.0	14.42	14.69	6.51	6.47	1.77
$\text{Ni}[\text{R}_{ClAc}]_2$	Yellow	5.0—5.5	13.63	13.73	6.49	6.55	3.32
$\text{Fe}[\text{R}_{ClAc}]_3$	Vermillion red	1.5—2.0	9.12	9.16	6.76	6.89	5.94
$\text{Al}[\text{R}_{ClAc}]_3$	White	4.5—5.0	4.59	4.65	7.15	7.24	—
$\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{R}_{ClAc})_2$	Deep violet	1.5—2.0	11.08	11.25	6.10	6.18	Dia
$\text{UO}_2(\text{OH})(\text{R}_{ClAc})$	Orange yellow	5.0—5.5	50.44	50.48	2.91	2.97	—

Further works with such ligands are in progress.

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Received November 11, 1966.